

Cross-Participant Synthesis

(All Participants)

1. Participant Overview

Ten participants completed this study. Participants were included based on their varying levels of experience, which allowed me to determine how each participant's familiarity with VR influenced their comparative evaluations. Table 1.1 lists participant characteristics.

Table 1.1: *Participant Characteristics*

ID	Play Order	Gaming Background	VR Experience	Final Preference
P01	VR → PC	Extensive PC	Moderate	Conditional VR
P02	PC → VR	Regular	Novice	Conditional VR
P03	PC → VR	Daily	Moderate	Strong VR
P04	PC → VR	Moderate	Novice	Conditional VR
P05	PC → VR	Diverse PC	Moderate	Conditional VR
P06	VR → PC	Regular PC	Novice	Strong VR
P07	VR → PC	Casual	Moderate	Conditional PC
P08	PC → VR	Extensive Daily	Novice	Strong VR
P09	VR → PC	Active PC	Experienced	Strong VR
P10	VR → PC	Extensive PC	Novice	Conditional VR

2. Key Findings by Theme

Seven themes were constructed from the analysis. Six of these seven themes came about as a result of converging trends within the overall group. The seventh theme represents cross-cutting findings from several themes that are interrelated.

Theme 1: Embodied Presence

Embodied Presence represents how the participants experienced being inside their virtual bodies, and how they perceived scale and height, as well as the ability to physically interact with their motion-tracked virtual hands inside the game environment. This theme is very closely aligned with Kiltner et al.'s (2012) three aspects of a person's SoE (Self-Location, Agency, and BO), and also to Slater's (2009) concept of PI and Psi. This theme was prominent across eight of ten participants, making it the central theme of their experience.

Pattern 1: VR Created Stronger Sense of Presence (10/10 Participants)

All ten people agreed they felt more "present" when playing the game in VR than in non-VR. The PC version was consistently described as controlling a character, whereas VR was described as being the character. These findings are consistent with previous studies comparing the presence benefits of VR (Carroll et al., 2019) and the FIVE framework's predictions (Slater & Wilbur, 1997), which stated that increased immersion will produce increased presence. Furthermore, these consistent findings, regardless of prior gaming background, level of exposure to VR experiences, or the order in which participants played each game, suggest there is a significant difference in how users experience games in VR versus non-VR platforms in general.

P01: *"I think in VR it felt higher and more around you. I think it was of course more immersive in some way. When you're there, it does feel like, Oh, it's really high."*

P02: *"I mean, it's both, like, because of the VR headset, you are, like, seeing literally the first person and, like, feeling like you are the person. But also, like, I think some of the interactions, such as the ladder and all the other stuff, like, feel more like in real life, definitely, compared to the PC. Because in the PC, you just press a keyboard or something. But, like, the VR one, you both, like, grab it, like, hold it, you press a button too, but you also, like, move your arms and stuff accordingly, like, like, in the, in real life movement."*

P03: *"For me, I had no problem with the height itself, like that I was in fear or something, or in fear of my character, with the PC version. But it was just more immersive in VR, because the PC, like the desktop version, the PC version was just not, you didn't really care about the height. It was just nice visuals, but in VR, it was just more personal, like I'm affected by the height. I mean, you're not, but it felt like it."*

P04: *"So, the VR was more evident, the difference between heights. It was much more evident because of the depth that you can feel in the VR that you cannot feel it that much in non-VR version, and the dystopian part, well, I think similarly in the VR version, it was more, it was because of the embedded immersion. I think you could feel it more."*

P05: *"In the screen-based one, it's kind of just an animation that happens, and in VR, it's something where I feel like, oh, this is doing something to me. So, I kind of have like this feeling of being actually moved in some way. It doesn't really feel like on a slack line, yeah, for sure, but at least I have this feeling of, oh, yeah, something's happening here."*

P06: *"I felt more present in the VR actually because I felt like the environment was created specifically for VR. Like, the environment when I look around and interactive objects like the ladder and other things, like interacting with the enemies also, it felt like it was made for VR and I enjoyed that."*

P07: *"I think for me the presence was more, you know, I felt the presence significantly in VR. However, if I talk about, you know, the comfort or immersiveness or that aspect, I think it was better in Windows PC. However, the presence, you know, itself, I mean, this game, I'm inside this game, this feelings was better in VR."*

P08: *"Um, if it's in terms of presence, uh I think the VR version was more appropriate to me. Um, I think um the first question was which version do I prefer and I think there are certain circumstances or certain points in which I think uh both of the VR and non-VR version have their advantages and disadvantages. So in terms of presence I think I prefer the VR version because in that version I feel more immersed and sort of like more present there."*

P09: *"I think I would be inclined towards the VR version, mostly because how you like perceive the environment and mostly how it feels to be up close and personal with the game. So, for example, you can see your hands in the game. That's like one step into immersion. So, you have to physically touch the bots to disable them, whereas on the PC version you*

don't have that. So, that's kind of like a huge difference between the desktop and the VR version."

P10: *"Definitely the VR one, because it gave me a feeling as if I was present inside the game. It definitely felt more real and I enjoyed it more."*

Participants' use of language in describing their experiences was diverse: "around you" (P01), "being the person" (P02), "personal" (P03), "depth that you can feel" (P04), "this is doing something to me" (P05), "it felt like it was made for VR and I enjoyed that." (P06), "I'm inside this game" (P07), "I feel more immersed and sort of like more present there" (P08), "up close and personal" (P09), and "inside the game" (P10). The variety in language used by the participants suggests they are describing an authentic phenomenological experience for which everyday language lacks consistent vocabulary, and is consistent with the complexity of presence as a psychological construct. This has motivated Schubert et al. (2001) to develop a factor-analytic presence scale identifying its distinct components. In spite of the differences in how participants describe the experience, all participants agreed that VR created a qualitatively different experience regarding 'presence' than PC did.

Pattern 2: Height and Scale Felt More Impactful in VR (9/10 Participants)

Nine participants described height, or scale, to be more intense, real, and impactful when they were in VR, which is similar to past research about height perception (Krupić et al., 2021; Gromer et al., 2019). The use of stereoscopic vision and life-size proportions caused the vertical distance to have a sense of consequence, while the same geometry felt like a flat visual on their non-VR screen. The lone exception was P07, who reported having no significant height response on either platform.

P01: *"I think in VR it felt higher and more around you. I think it was of course more immersive in some way. When you're there, it does feel like, Oh, it's really high."*

P02: *"Um, like, the height-wise, it does affect, especially when you're, like, in the monkey bar or, like, when you're, um, in the zipline and stuff. It, it affects, I think, in the VR, it, um, feels taller, and, like, you, uh, look down and, like, it feels like you can actually fall, and it's, like, you're in the actual height, and that's, in the sense, it affects the dystopian thingy, I would say."*

P03: *"But, like, from the immersion, everything is just bigger. Because, on PC, everything is just on your small screen. But, in VR, it's just, I know it's just the default Unreal Engine models. But, if it's something, if it's life size, it's just more threatening."*

P04: *"Yeah, in the VR, the feeling, that feeling is more intense. That was more intense... So, in the normal game, or, I mean, not, sorry, sorry, in the non-VR. In the non-VR, it's not very, how to say, I mean, it is less intense, much, or maybe much less intense. But in the VR one, it is more intense."*

P05: *"I think VR gives me a much better sense of scale. I realized that, no, I didn't realize, I noticed that kind of, I was kind of trying to look around much more in VR than I was in the, in the mouse and keyboard thing. So basically I was, in one place I was just standing there like looking over the level and being like, yeah, this is kind of a big area here that I get to occupy... There's just a stereoscopic view of something and the micro-movement that I get to do that gives me a sense of scale of the whole environment. I think that's much better in VR."*

P06: *"To be honest, when I was playing in PC, that height didn't matter actually, to be honest. But for the VR version, I felt it—really felt it, like when I'm going up and looking down from the high height, and the environment was really great, and I felt that height comparison in the VR actually."*

P08: *"Um, yes definitely the perception was a bit different. Um, I felt like um when i was playing in the non-VR version for me it was um mostly all the areas felt a little bit of similar to me. But when i played on the VR version, I sort of felt the differences a little bit more in general. Like I used to pinpoint certain areas like okay this is a little bit different than the other. But in the non-VR version more or less the areas felt a little bit of similar to me."*

P09: *"On the VR version you also have like a sense of scale. So, overall pacing, you can like go through the PC version easily, but on VR your brain kind of tricks you to take it slow and be careful. So, yeah, the VR."*

P10: *"Definitely, it's the VR, because of the scale that you can feel in the environment, the ladder, the rope, the zipline, everything felt like, life-like, because of the scale according to the real human. The height of the robot, the depth that I would feel while looking down from buildings felt like very real, which resulted in better embodiment of the character."*

P09's observation that "it tricks you to take it slow and be careful" shows how increased presence affected behavior while playing the game. The participants didn't just see things

differently in terms of height, but acted upon them differently, supporting Slater's (2009) claim that increased presence leads to realistic behavioral reactions to virtual stimuli.

Pattern 3: *Physical Enactment Valued Over Button-Press Abstraction (10/10 Participants)*

Participants universally preferred the physical enactment provided by VR, over the abstracted button-presses provided by the PC platform. A common theme in participant feedback was that non-VR interactions were boring, dull, or forgettable. This finding provides direct support for the natural mapping framework (Reer et al., 2022; Skalski et al., 2011): VR's combination of tangible and KNM (physical controllers and body tracking corresponding to real-world movements) was preferred over PC's directional mapping (abstracted controls).

P01: *"It was more fun to climb the ladder, even though I had troubles at first. At some point I had fun climbing the ladder actively rather than just pressing button and waiting on the PC. On the PC, I just press a button and then I just move up and it's like... okay, five seconds, ten seconds, okay I'm up. So it was quite dull."*

P02: *"The ladder one was cool. I thought, oh, this is actually so cool to do it like this. Because also it was the first interaction that actually like changed a lot in the VR version, and felt realistic."*

P03: *"I guess the PC version, it felt almost a bit redundant, because you just press one button, or you usually, in usual games, don't need to do much to climb a ladder, and in VR, it was more, oh God, I really need to, Um, I need to put effort into climbing, but it was just a completely different thing."*

P04: *"Because you are imagining that you are in that world and you are part of the world. So, this feel is better presented in the VR version [Talking about interactions]."*

P05: *"For me personally, I would give a slight edge to the VR version because, in general, I can be very immersed in any type of screen-based gaming as well... In this particular case, for example, like looking over the edge of something that's a very steep fall I could fall down from. This is something that is definitely more. I feel this is more something that could happen to me in VR than in the keyboard and mouse or controller-based stuff. Also, basically, with a controller-based game, you don't get like this type of leaning forward looking over the edge and looking straight down."*

P06: *"It was like I am really interacting. It was not in a negative way but in a positive way—like I am actually interacting. For example, using the rope when I was interacting with it and going forward, it felt good, like I am interacting in the real world."*

P07: *"It was natural, and, I think it's all of the functionalities there. Like, disabling the AI or everything. That was much more alive in the VR version."*

P08: *"Yeah, so um, um again I would say like in the non-VR version it was like, uh, effortless... but in the VR version there were a lot of this interactable moment in which you have to do certain actions. In each of these um individual moments you have to do different sort of action. Like for the lever you have to pull it up, for the button you have to press it down. So you're sort of using your gesture, you're using your hands, you're using that to do it... So, um, in terms of experience these are, I think they are, these are, um, little experiences but i think these are very fun experiences."*

P09: *"Well, it's like a totally different experience, especially the lever. I like that, and pressing down on things like that gives you like a very good immersion... Yeah, definitely [natural to see button and press it]."*

P10: *"Climbing the ladder, like, physically was more fun because I felt like I was actually doing something rather than controlling a character in a game. So I would vote for the VR in this case."*

P10's differentiation between "actually doing something," and "controlling a character," illustrates the do vs command distinction that is central to natural mapping. P01's account was also significant: Although initially experiencing difficulty with VR climbing, they stated that the experience was "more fun" than the PC's linear climbing experience, which was "dull". The results suggest that the engagement value of physically doing something may be able to override the ease-of-use value.

Pattern 4: Emotional Amplification Through Presence (7/10 Participants)

Seven participants (P03, P04, P06, P07, P08, P09, P10) reported there was a relation between perceived immersion and their level of emotional response. They also expressed how concerned they were for their characters and what they were doing. This is consistent with Gall et al.'s (2021) finding that illusory embodiment (virtual BO) intensifies emotional responses to virtual stimuli. Three participants (P01, P02, P05) did not perceive or respond emotionally to any increase in their level of immersion.

P03: *"Definitely, when I was almost shot, because the animation was like this, or, actually, I don't remember what it was, but this... But, in the right moment, I was able to disable him, and that it was frozen in this frame that I almost got shot was just very... How do you say? How do you say in English? Exciting? Thrilling? Dangerous? Yeah."*

P04: *"Yeah, in the VR, the feeling, that feeling is more intense. That was more intense... So, in the normal game, or, I mean, not, sorry, sorry, in the non-VR. In the non-VR, it's not very, how to say, I mean, it is less intense, much, or maybe much less intense. But in the VR one, it is more intense."*

P06: *"I actually did in the VR version. I actually felt it, to be honest. For example, in the last section when I had to disarm the robots—that was an intense moment when there were three or four robots going around and I had to sit and go slowly to interact with them, to hide from them and to interact with them. That was quite a fascinating moment in that game which I didn't feel in the PC."*

P07: *"Yeah, I think it's the VR one. It's the VR one. I felt more alive there."*

P08: *"Definitely I felt more anxious because, because yeah, it was very up close with the robots... it felt like a little bit of threatening, like more threatening than the non-VR version."*

P09: *"Uh, so in the VR version, I cared for the player. So, when he got shot or like got into sticky situations, then yeah, that felt like I was in the player's shoes. So, that felt personal. But on the PC version, I didn't care if he died or what or like if I lost. So, I didn't care anything."*

P10: *"The VR version was more stressing due to the scale of the surroundings. For some reason, in the PC version, dying or getting caught wasn't that stressing. But in VR, I actually cared about not getting caught or shot by the robots, probably because I felt more present in the world in VR."*

Divergence: Height Fear Activation

Nine participants noted they had greater height perception; however, only four of them (P02, P04, P05, and P09) reported experiencing an emotional response related to fear. Interestingly,

two of the nine participants who reported having a self-identified “height” phobia (P01 & P06) did not report experiencing fear regarding the VR heights. Gromer et al. (2019) found that presence-related emotional arousal created higher levels of felt presence; however, they found no evidence that increasing the level of experimentally induced presence would also increase the level of fear responses, which explains P01 and P06’s non-activation of height-induced phobia even when they reported enhanced height perception in VR.

Height triggered emotional response (4/10):

P02: *"Um, like, the height-wise, it does affect, especially when you're, like, in the monkey bar or, like, when you're, um, in the zipline and stuff. It, it affects, I think, in the VR, it, um, feels taller, and, like, you, uh, look down and, like, it feels like you can actually fall, and it's, like, you're in the actual height, and that's, in the sense, it affects the dystopian thingy, I would say."*

P04: *"Yeah, in the VR, the feeling, that feeling is more intense. That was more intense."*

P05: *"For me personally, I would give a slight edge to the VR version because, in general, I can be very immersed in any type of screen-based gaming as well... In this particular case, for example, like looking over the edge of something that's a very steep fall I could fall down from. This is something that is definitely more. I feel this is more something that could happen to me in VR than in the keyboard and mouse or controller-based stuff. Also, basically, with a controller-based game, you don't get like this type of leaning forward looking over the edge and looking straight down."*

P09: *"On the VR version you also have like a sense of scale. So, overall pacing, you can like go through the PC version easily, but on VR your brain kind of tricks you to take it slow and be careful. So, yeah, the VR."*

Height perceived but no fear (5/10):

P01: *"I didn't, even though I have the fear of heights, I didn't feel it in this game in particular. You saw me jumping down from there because there's no fall damage, and I cheated my way a little bit there."*

P03: *"For me, I had no problem with the height itself, like that I was in fear or something, or in fear of my character, with the PC version. But it was just more immersive in VR, because the PC, like the desktop version, the PC version was just not, you didn't*

really care about the height. It was just nice visuals, but in VR, it was just more personal, like I'm affected by the height. I mean, you're not, but it felt like it."

P06: *"From my previous experiences, I feel some motion sickness while moving. But in this case, I didn't feel that, to be honest. I actually didn't feel that. I moved smoothly and rotated around. Even I looked down from the height—I have height phobia—so when I look down, I should have felt something, but I didn't."*

P07: *"I think height wasn't actually that kind of an issue to talk about because I didn't really feel anything like significant here. Like, that's something I have to talk about. I think it was all quite normal."*

P10: *"The VR version felt more real because of the depth. In VR, I felt the heights in a more realistic way."*

A possible explanation for this finding is that P01 attributed their lack of fear to their understanding of game mechanics, which may have diminished the Psi. In other words, while P01 felt greater perceived height perception (i.e., achieved PI), the fact that he knew there were no consequences to falling diminished his Psi (he believed what he was seeing was not real). Therefore, it appears that feeling perceptually present and feeling emotional response are not the same thing. You can be perceptually present in a virtual environment, yet fail to respond emotionally to a similar real-life event.

Contradictory Case: P07

P07 demonstrated a sense of being “inside” the game (spatial presence); however, they reported experiencing an inability to move around as hoped (“stuck”), and therefore did not report any of the height effects which would be indicative of embodiment in the character. Therefore, it appears that P07 experienced Self-Location but did not achieve the full Agency or BO that is necessary for the embodiment of a character, demonstrating that all of the elements of embodiment do not necessarily appear together.

Theme 2: Comfort Negotiation

The Comfort Negotiation theme captures how users managed their physical comfort, motion sickness, hardware ergonomic issues, and session duration limits. This theme relates to research on cybersickness (Biswas et al., 2024; Weech et al., 2019), as well as research that recommends treating user comfort as an additional evaluative dimension when evaluating VR games (Sweetser & Rogalewicz, 2020). Comfort was never the primary concern for any particular participant, but comfort was always one of the factors that participants evaluated when they were considering different platforms for evaluation.

Pattern 1: *Motion Sickness Absent or Manageable (10/10 Participants)*

None of the participants experienced motion sickness that was bad enough for them to stop mid-way during the test phase. Six participants stated they did not experience any symptoms (P01, P03, P06, P07, P08, P09), while four participants said they experienced some mild symptoms that were manageable (P02, P04, P05, P10). This relatively favorable comfort level of this participant group compares well to studies indicating high cybersickness rates (Biswas et al., 2024). One possible reason for the favorable comfort rate is the slower pace of the stealth-traversal game. A final possible explanation is that the session length is within established sickness threshold limits. It is interesting that none of the participants experienced severe motion sickness since it was an experiment where participants used continuous locomotion in most cases, which has been shown by Clifton and Palmisano (2020) to cause more motion sickness in general.

No symptoms (6/10 — P01, P03, P06, P07, P08, P09):

P01: *"I think there was a bit of discomfort from just headset itself because of this strap and everything, because this basic strap is, you know, it's bad."*

P03: *"Um, not the game, like, no, just, sometimes I get a headache, but from the headset itself, from the weight, or because I did not adjust properly, or whatever, but not from the game itself."*

P06: *"From my previous experiences, I feel some motion sickness while moving. But in this case, I didn't feel that, to be honest. I actually didn't feel that. I moved smoothly and rotated around. Even I looked down from the height—I have height phobia—so when I look down, I should have felt something, but I didn't."*

P07: *"Did you experience any motion sickness, nausea or any kind of dizziness, eye strain during the VR gameplay?"... "No."... "Was everything good?"... "Everything was good."*

P08: *"Well, I, uh, no not necessarily, but I felt a little bit of weight on my head and a little bit of eye strain. Because, I think, I, um, sort of like messed up with the focus thing, I felt like I did it well. But at some points some particular angles or some particular things did become a little bit of blurry. But, um, those are not very big issues, very small issues. But overall, yes I had a very good experience, nothing that severe."*

P09: *"No, it was pretty much like a moderate experience, nothing extreme."*

Mild/manageable symptoms (4/10 — P02, P04, P05, P10):

P02: *"I felt a bit of motion sickness, yes... Walking. Not all the time, but at some parts walking, and maybe the ladder or the monkey bar a bit too, not a lot, not super disturbing."*

P04: *"Well, at first, I had dizziness. It was more, my dizziness was more, and it was a, a bit challenging for me. After some time, I got used to it. It became much better. But then, after some time, I got a little bit tired."*

P05: *"Like 20 minutes of VR gives me a very slight dizziness always. So this is not really tied to this experience but I had this here too. So I did have like this this moment where I'm like yeah I'm kind of it was enjoyable but I was also kind of glad that I now got to take off the headset again. Because I think if I think if it was twice as long I probably would have needed to pause at this point. So like after like half an hour or 45 minutes for sure I think I would have just needed a break."*

P10: *"Mostly no, though I felt a bit dizzy after I took off the VR headset from my head, probably because my eyes were still adjusting."*

Pattern 2: Comfort–Enjoyment Dissociation (9/10 Participants)

Nine participants (P01, P02, P03, P04, P05, P06, P07, P08, P10) expressed their preference for PC due to the comfort factor; however, nine users preferred VR in the end, demonstrating an identifiable conceptualization of comfort and enjoyment as two independent factors with enjoyment weighing higher within manageable thresholds. P09 was the most experienced VR

user in this study, and did not reference comfort when comparing the two devices. This research extended Weech et al.'s (2019) review of the relationship between presence and cybersickness and shows that the users who are aware of the trade-off between the comfort and immersion of VR will intentionally evaluate these two aspects of their experience separately.

P01: *"I would rather play it in VR, even though I said that PC version was more overall kind of nice. I think I would prefer a bit edited and better version of VR. In this particular case I felt like it was more comfortable to play on PC, but I would love to play in VR because I feel like this interactivity is good for VR. These ladders and tapping and pushing buttons—it's all working well. You see your hands."*

P02: *"For this particular game, I would say you can compromise the, like, I mean you can choose the VR version. But some of them needs to be a bit shorter maybe, some of these interactions, and it depends, like, if it's like super uncomfortable, I would prefer the PC one for example."*

P03: *"The productivity, because you're just... everything is a bit more fast. [Identifying PC's distinguishing advantage]"*

P04: *"So, if the convenience part and the comfort is same as the PC, then I will go with VR."*

P05: *"Like 20 minutes of VR gives me a very slight dizziness always. So this is not really tied to this experience but I had this here too. So I did have like this this moment where I'm like yeah I'm kind of it was enjoyable but I was also kind of glad that I now got to take off the headset again. Because I think if I think if it was twice as long I probably would have needed to pause at this point. So like after like half an hour or 45 minutes for sure I think I would have just needed a break."*

P06: *"For the comfort one, I will say the PC. But for the interaction side, I will definitely say VR—it was really fun in VR interactions."*

P07: *"Just the movement. Like I was free. I was free in the game, and, you know, the rest of the things I think VR was pretty good, but the overall experience, so all of it, like, when you combine, like, the smoothness of Windows was way better."*

P08: *"Um, I think accessibility, that like I've speaking about it a lot, because, uh, and also, um, yeah the accessibility the first thing. Because the control schemes and the tasks are like, those are very easy to do and you don't have to like look around and find stuff. You can just you know use your right stick to like control the camera and everything. So*

basically, um, it's a very relaxed way to play a video game, like the non-VR version was a very relaxed way."

P10: *"I can play on the PC version for at least a couple of hours while on the VR, it would mostly be around 40 to 45 minutes. Though, I enjoyed VR more, and my session was a bit longer than 45 minutes, I was feeling a bit tired."*

Pattern 3: Session Duration Limits (7/10 Participants)

Seven participants (P02, P03, P05, P06, P08, P09, P10) estimated their time limits for a VR session as being from thirty to sixty minutes and indicated that they could spend hours using a non-VR platform to play games, which is consistent with studies of cybersickness (Petri et al., 2020; da Silva Marinho et al., 2022) that indicate VR gaming is limited by temporal boundaries that do not affect traditional gaming.

P02: *"For this particular game, I would say you can compromise the, like, I mean you can choose the VR version. But some of them needs to be a bit shorter maybe, some of these interactions, and it depends, like, if it's like super uncomfortable, I would prefer the PC one for example."*

P03: *"So, since there are much more sensors included in VR, you definitely get exhausted faster. Yeah, but not in a bad way. Just because you are just more engaged, in any case."*

P05: *"Like 20 minutes of VR gives me a very slight dizziness always. So this is not really tied to this experience but I had this here too. So I did have like this this moment where I'm like yeah I'm kind of it was enjoyable but I was also kind of glad that I now got to take off the headset again. Because I think if I think if it was twice as long I probably would have needed to pause at this point. So like after like half an hour or 45 minutes for sure I think I would have just needed a break."*

P06: *"I can play for an hour in PC, of course. But for VR, I guess half an hour or less, I guess."*

P08: *"So, do you think you kind of like went, uh, around 40 minutes in the VR version straight. Do you think it was fine or do you think it would have been better if you could take some rest in between?... Um, I think it would have been better if i took some rest."*

P09: *"I think an hour at most."*

P10: *"I can play on the PC version for at least a couple of hours while on the VR, it would mostly be around 40 to 45 minutes. Though, I enjoyed VR more, and my session was a bit longer than 45 minutes, I was feeling a bit tired."*

Pattern 4: Willingness to Sacrifice Comfort for VR (6/10 Participants)

Six of the participants (P01, P02, P03, P06, P09, P10) were willing to accept the immersive quality of VR over non-VR platforms' comfort levels. Among the participants, many of them were specific about their willingness to do so based on the genre of game they were playing. P05 stated to switch back to PC for longer gaming sessions, while P07 indicated a preference for PC over VR, primarily because of the difficulties with locomotion. This is an example of participants making active choices to experience a certain level of discomfort in exchange for what they felt would be a satisfactory level of enjoyment.

P01: *"I would rather play it in VR, even though I said that PC version was more overall kind of nice. I think I would prefer a bit edited and better version of VR. In this particular case I felt like it was more comfortable to play on PC, but I would love to play in VR because I feel like this interactivity is good for VR. These ladders and tapping and pushing buttons—it's all working well. You see your hands."*

P02: *"For this particular game, I would say you can compromise the, like, I mean you can choose the VR version. But some of them needs to be a bit shorter maybe, some of these interactions, and it depends, like, if it's like super uncomfortable, I would prefer the PC one for example."*

P03: *"I wouldn't mind getting used to... Motion controllers?... Yeah. Like, I would sacrifice the keyboard."*

P06: *"Will you be willing to sacrifice the comfort... to play the VR version?"... "I definitely will."*

P09: *"So, will you be willing to sacrifice comfort of playing in a PC to enjoy the immersion in VR?... Yes."*

P10: *"I think it depends on the genre of the game. If the game has a lot of physical reactions like this one, then I would sacrifice the comfort to enjoy VR's immersion."*

Theme 3: Control & Agency

Control and Agency captures the participant's experiences of movement, rotation, and responsiveness to their input inside the game environment. While VR was able to provide a high level of discrete physical interaction, movement was described as being VR's least successful aspect. The theme relates to the agency component of Kiltner et al.'s (2012) embodiment framework, as well as McMahan et al.'s (2016) interaction fidelity concept. This theme dominated two participants' views of the overall experience that had the highest number of frustrations associated with control (P01, P07).

Pattern 1: *Missing Lateral Movement as Critical Deficiency (6/10 Participants)*

The lack of strafing was a significant issue for six participants (P01, P05, P06, P07, P08, P09). The single absence of strafing was the reason for P07 preferring PC over VR.

P01: *"I immediately wanted to strafe left and right like I do here, but I couldn't for some reason on VR. I can only move front and back and that really disturbed me. I'm like, 'Okay, I really need to move sides' because this is what in most VR games you do."*

P05: *"For the most part the Xbox controller also because of strafing because it's just a style that I play in. I'm basically never going in a straight line in a shooter type game. Also in a third person type game I'm probably also constantly doing the left and right thing around corners and stuff like that. So with that I was more used to it and it felt more like the default I'm used to."*

P06: *"In this case, it's of course PC because it was really easy for me to interact in PC. In some cases in VR, when I am interacting with the bots and we are face to face, I can't go behind it and disable him. So if he is facing me, it's certain that I am dying and re-spawning."*

P07: *"I think, like when I played other games in VR, where I personally had the control to go, you know, move left or right, and it wasn't really present there, and I was always going forward and backward and moving with this, and it wasn't really, I mean, I wanted the right and left movement. I think if I had left and right movement, I would have chosen VR over Windows game for this project."*

P08: *"Would you have preferred that you could move just like you move in the PC version, in the VR too? Rather than having this head-based movement would you have preferred to move like a normal controller thumbstick movement, left right, and forward, and backward"*

in any direction?... Uh, I think that would have been, um, much more easier to control I think. Because that's the control scheme that, uh, we usually use in non-VR games. So for me, I think, uh, I think that would have been a better experience for me personally."

P09: *"I would say like not being able to move left to right on the VR version, that's the only thing."*

Pattern 2: PC Movement Easier Due to Familiarity (10/10 Participants)

All of the participants preferred PC movement over VR movement, and attributed their preference primarily to the familiarity of the controls as opposed to the actual superior nature of the controls on either platform. This supports H2 and is in line with Kojić et al.'s (2023) finding that user factors, including prior VR experience, influence user preferences and technology affinity in VR contexts.

P01: *"Traversal—the movement. As I said, the strafe to sides and the camera rotation. I think this is why it was comfortable and more natural to play for me on PC, and I completed it faster just because of that."*

P02: *"Because of the controllers, too, actually, because the moving controllers, and, like, in PC, I could move, actually, very fast, and, like, disable them, and I wouldn't mind, you know. But in the other one I had to change the direction, and stuff, and it, I couldn't really get into that, uh, control, uh, very fast, so, it felt a bit anxious."*

P03: *"Yes, it was a bit more. I personally didn't like the way you, the locomotion, it was just, I mean, of course, you could also tilt your head and then you change direction as well. But, to be very fast, and sometimes you needed to be fast, maybe because of the robots, and then it was a bit annoying to change direction with, with, what was the, how was the button called, where you, thumbstick?... Right, thumbstick, thumbstick. Yeah, that's the only thing, the locomotion, otherwise, it was more satisfying in VR."*

P04: *"By, by, by, because I'm used to it. So, when I want to open a door, I press a button in a video game. When I want to go, like, for example, for a ladder, it depends on the game also. So, so, so, in some games, it's just a combination of first pressing a button and then going up or down... Uh, but overall, because I'm used to the non-VR version, that one was easier for me to get the control, to have the, uh, how to say, to implementation of the control was easier for me to understand."*

P05: *"I have a little bit of a caveat there because I'm very used to the Xbox controller. That is the layout that I'm very familiar with. It's the same one on the like Arrow GLI or on the Xbox that I play at home and stuff like that. So that is something where I know oh I press X. That's just memory. What's it called? Muscle memory basically, and on the quest controllers I constantly needed to read oh I press X for that. Oh where's X again? Oh it's over here."*

P06: *"For the movement, it is easier for me to control in PC, of course, as I play mostly in PC. But in VR, I didn't feel like I am being stuck or I can't control the player at all—I didn't feel like that. But in some cases in VR, I couldn't find out which way to go."*

P07: *"Just the movement. Like I was free. I was free in the game, and, you know, the rest of the things I think VR was pretty good, but the overall experience, so all of it, like, when you combine, like, the smoothness of Windows was way better."*

P08: *"Um, definitely the non-VR version was easier. Because, um, once again I have, uh, familiarities with the controls with the gamepad or with the non-VR games. So like it was, um, sort of like a muscle memory to me. So I didn't have much difficulties controlling the player with the controller. But in the VR version again I had to learn a lot of things. Um, there is nothing in my muscle memory. So the camera movement and the, uh, the rotational movement and the character movement, I had a little difficulty with the synergies, to perform the synergies with those things."*

P09: *"PC was easier to learn... Just because like, it's the familiar layout for PC. So, you kind of expect which button to do what, but in VR, that's more like real life. But in this game, yes, there is like a, you expected something to do, some kind of interaction then it did."*

P10: *"PC version provided me more freedom to explore the surroundings, because again, I am more familiar with the PC controls. So it naturally came to me and I wasn't stressed about it, the controls at all. It was like mostly muscle memories kicking."*

Divergent Pattern: Rotation Style Preference

The preference for the rotation mechanic was divided. Five participants (P01, P02, P03, P08, P10) wanted the option to rotate smoothly, and one participant (P09) preferred the snap-rotation that was implemented in the VR version of the game. Four participants were unsure or did not have an opinion about it. The preference for snap-rotation by P09 was directly related to

managing motion sickness. These results show the need for developers of VR games to allow users to customize their locomotion options rather than deciding on just one.

Preferred snap rotation (1/10 — P09):

P09: *"Yeah, that helps with motion sickness for me... Yeah, I would not prefer that [smooth rotation]. I'm more inclined towards using snap and like, for smaller adjustment, I can just move myself."*

Preferred smooth rotation (5/10 — P01, P02, P03, P08, P10):

P01: *"Also, with the right stick, the movement was choppy—you move and it's choppy. Whereas on PC it's smooth. I also would love maybe in VR game to be smoother motion of right stick."*

P02: *"Uh, I didn't like the moving in VR, which is always a tricky thing, because, like, whether it's teleportation or just, like, moving like that is just, like, um, annoying. Maybe if it was just, you can, um, the turning around was not, you know, like, snapping, but also smooth, maybe would feel a bit better, moving wise."*

P03: *"Um, yes, like, I think there are some people who don't like the smooth rotation or smooth movement in general... Yes, I don't have a problem with it, but, um, maybe a suggestion... maybe even if you only move your head for some centimeters, maybe in VR, you turn around for, for even more degrees."*

P08: *"Um, I think at first I need to experience that myself, because I don't know, if like, uh, people get dizzy or motion sickness in general, in that smooth camera movement. But I think I would have preferred the smooth camera movements. Definitely, yeah."*

P10: *"I would say the controls were much easier to get a grasp on PC. It was not because the VR had bad controls, but rather because I'm more familiar with the layout on PC. I also love the head-based movement in VR, but I would have preferred if the rotation was smooth rather than snapping to certain degrees."*

Theme 4: Learning & Adaptation

Learning and Adaptation reflect on the ways participants became competent at using the VR mechanics, and how difficulty in acquiring knowledge was connected to how satisfied they were with their experience. The Learning and Adaptation theme was constructed from the research data as an additional theme beyond those that had been initially hypothesized.

Pattern 1: PC Familiarity as Accessibility Baseline (10/10 Participants)

Every participant acknowledged that years of accumulated experience and muscle memory gave the non-VR version an inherent ease-of-use advantage. Participants understood this as a familiarity bias and not as a superiority of the non-VR version over the VR version of the game.

P01: *"Traversal—the movement. As I said, the strafe to sides and the camera rotation. I think this is why it was comfortable and more natural to play for me on PC, and I completed it faster just because of that."*

P02: *"Um, the thing is, I always played games. Like, I mean, I usually play games on keyboard and mouse. So, when I was playing in PC, it was the basic stuff, like, moving and, like, pressing just a button and something, like, those stuff were a bit more intuitive than VR."*

P03: *"Uh, I guess, um, the PC version, everything, the whole, um, like, every mechanic. Um, also because, maybe it's just because of Unreal Engine, but, um, the gameplay of the PC version was very smooth, everything very, very nice, very same as well."*

P04: *"By, by, by, because I'm used to it. So, when I want to open a door, I press a button in a video game. When I want to go, like, for example, for a ladder, it depends on the game also. So, so, so, in some games, it's just a combination of first pressing a button and then going up or down... Uh, but overall, because I'm used to the non-VR version, that one was easier for me to get the control, to have the, uh, how to say, to implementation of the control was easier for me to understand."*

P05: *"I have a little bit of a caveat there because I'm very used to the Xbox controller. That is the layout that I'm very familiar with. It's the same one on the like Arrow GLI or on the Xbox that I play at home and stuff like that. So that is something where I know oh I press X. That's just memory. What's it called? Muscle memory basically, and on the quest*

controllers I constantly needed to read oh I press X for that. Oh where's X again? Oh it's over here."

P06: *"For the movement, it is easier for me to control in PC, of course, as I play mostly in PC."*

P07: *"The thing is, the Windows version was better... Then it, and I think the reason behind this is that I'm really much more comfortable with Windows version as I'm playing it. I think I was in, I think my age was four, three or four when I first started to play computer games. So, I think there's a comfort, of course."*

P08: *"Definitely, yeah. The years of experience of playing video games, that's definitely there."*

P09: *"PC was easier to learn... Just because like, it's the familiar layout for PC. So, you kind of expect which button to do what, but in VR, that's more like real life. But in this game, yes, there is like a, you expected something to do, some kind of interaction then it did."*

P10: *"I would again say PC as I'm quite familiar with the layout of the PC version. I am probably a bit biased towards it."*

Pattern 2: Ladder Mechanics Required Learning (9/10 Participants)

Nine participants (P01, P02, P03, P04, P05, P06, P08, P09, P10) experienced initial confusion at first when using the VR ladder mechanic regarding whether to hold the rungs or side rails. Some participants mentioned they would be stuck if it weren't for the researchers' assistance. This is in line with what McMahan et al. (2016) said about users having expectations of how interactions should feel in VR. Participants used mental models that were from either actual climbing or from playing other games, which did not match the prototype's implementation of the VR ladder.

P01: *"I didn't find the control with the ladder intuitive for me personally, even though it's subject to controversy, of course. I thought I would climb ladder like this, and without your input I wouldn't have guessed it. I think I would just be stuck probably."*

P02: *"Yeah, yeah, I understand, but I think you explained. I don't remember what you exactly said, but I think I understood that I have to pull from the sides and not the bars, but,*

like, if you didn't tell me, I could actually, like, okay, like, maybe it's the bars, I could feel like that."

P03: *"Yes, but not because it was complicated designed, but because I need to remind myself that VR is actually so realistic, that you need to all the time adjust your hands to actually climb. It's, I was still used to pressing only one button. It was just this."*

P04: *"On the non-VR version, that was just with button, and you could, it was, it was, how to say, it was a more familiar experience to me. I'm kind of being used to that one, and that was easier, but on the VR, it was more difficult, and at first, it wasn't that much of a good feeling. Maybe a little later, it got better."*

P05: *"My first try was kind of going on the rungs, on the step things. I think it's rungs, right? So I'm not sure if this is something worth adding, because you don't have to go either or. You could just offer both if you want. But I'm also not sure if I'm like the only person or if it's just something that's universal that people would try this."*

P06: *"The PC version was usual—as I am just interacting with it and going up, nothing fancy. But for the VR version, I was a bit confused why I am holding the side bars and going up instead of holding the steps and going up. So it was new to me, to be honest."*

P08: *"Yes, I was definitely a little bit confused because, um, I believe there were no like text based or clear instructions when i was climbing the ladder, and as someone who haven't played many VR games for me that was new. So yeah it was a little confusing for me at the first, at the beginning."*

P09: *"Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first."*

P10: *"I enjoyed the ladder, though, like, I got confused when where to hold on the ladder at the start of the game."*

Pattern 3: Learning Difficulty Resolved into Satisfaction (7/10 Participants)

Seven participants (P03, P04, P06, P07, P08, P09, P10) went from being confused to competent, and many of them were satisfied with the effort they had to put in to complete a certain part of the experience. This finding supports SDT (Ryan et al., 2006) and the concept of competence satisfaction as a result of achieving mastery. The participants described the physical activity that caused “stress” as becoming “fun” once they were able to achieve competency, suggesting that VR evaluations based strictly on the initial reaction may misrepresent the overall quality of the user’s experience.

P03: *"So, it was a bit, of course, more demanding on the physical interactions for the VR. But, do you think it was also more satisfying?... Yeah... Because of that?... Yeah. I guess for me that's a good point."*

P04: *"With the VR one, it was more challenging because I'm not, I'm not used to. But also, it has the entertaining part also. So, so, the way of doing the interaction in VR, not maybe for, but overall, it was, uh, entertaining process."*

P06: *"Can you name any particular thing that you felt the VR version did way better than the PC version?... I guess there are multiple—the ladder system, the zipline system, and the rope also (Despite Ladder Mechanics Confusion)."*

P07: *"Exactly that, that experience, and I was going, I think from, at first, I made a mistake when I tried it from the first time, because I really didn't understand it quite. So, at that time, I sort of swung backward. But after that, I always used the rope technique, you know, the properly, in the forward, forward way, and it was really good, the experience was good. But the first one wasn't, that's the thing."*

P08: *"So climbing a ladder after playing this game in the VR version, before playing this game I did not have thought that climbing a ladder would be this much you know, uh, impactful or you have to put a lot of effort in this. So this was a new experience for me definitely, and um yeah definitely it was fun, it was fun, and also like when i had to put an effort on this particular action it felt a lot more meaningful for me. So yeah definitely it was a good experience. I had to learn first, I was failing a lot, but when i finally did it that was a very good feeling of accomplishment, yeah."*

P09: *"Yeah. Turns out it's very much fun to climb ladders in VR."*

P10: *"My answer would be the same. Though I struggled a lot with the rope, I finally completed it after seven to eight tries and it was quite satisfying. It demanded a lot of physical effort, which was at times stressing, but really entertaining in the end."*

Theme 5: Interaction Design

Interaction Design Quality refers to how well the game mechanics (buttons, levers, ladders, ropes, ziplines, and enemy interactions) were implemented and how naturally coherent each of them functioned in-game. This theme relates to Skarbez et al.'s (2017) point that coherence plays a significant role in creating a sense of Psi.

Pattern 1: *Button and Lever Interactions Universally Successful (10/10 Participants)*

All the participants were highly positive about the physicality of both button pressing and lever pulling as a means to interact in VR. These two mechanics had a direct alignment with how buttons and levers work in real life. The fact that P02 was able to see how a “very simple interaction” became engaging via its enactment illustrates that, in terms of the nature of content, VR’s enhancements do not necessarily have to be based on a high degree of complexity all the time.

P01: *"Smashing button was more fun... I think when something is up there and it's yellow and you just want to push it, this is just classic. I think, of virtual games—some interactivity. I think it's just natural to poke something or to push something. On the other hand, pressing X is just basically a button, that's it."*

P02: *"It was fun. I mean, it's, like, a very simple interaction. But even, like, just the fact that you can do that. Just do this, and it feels like a real button, instead of going there and pressing the keyboard or whatever. It's definitely, yeah, the button. It's better in VR."*

P03: *"Just in more satisfying, because, yeah, because you, you need to do a whole movement with your hand instead of just pressing E or something."*

P04: *"The lever also similar to that one. That one was maybe even better than the button. But I think for the button, that was done right and correctly. Lever. That one also was, like, similar to real world, and it was done in a good way, and it was convenient also."*

P05: *"This is better I think because there's... Of course these are like pretty obviously interactable element big levers. So not like in a flat where it's like a dilly dilly switch on the wall or something. So you can recognize them from far. So I don't really have an expectation how these would feel, and in some regards I have like an expectation how a button should feel or react. But for these levers I don't. So I don't... At least I don't mind as much. I think they were great. Also I think they had a little bit of amount of vibration going on, right?... I think this helps a little bit. These I would say work pretty well."*

P06: *"It was really good because, for example, for the lift I had to pull the lever and then interact with the lift. I felt it was really good, and also for the button when I am pressing it and it works. Compared to the PC version, it felt good to me."*

P07: *"It was natural, and, I think it's all of the functionalities there. Like, disabling the AI or everything. That was much more alive in the VR version."*

P08: *"Yeah, so um, um again I would say like in the non-VR version it was like, uh, effortless... but in the VR version there were a lot of this interactable moment in which you have to do certain actions. In each of these um individual moments you have to do different sort of action. Like for the lever you have to pull it up, for the button you have to press it down. So you're sort of using your gesture, you're using your hands, you're using that to do it... So, um, in terms of experience these are, I think they are, these are, um, little experiences but i think these are very fun experiences."*

P09: *"Well, it's like a totally different experience, especially the lever. I like that, and pressing down on things like that gives you like a very good immersion... Yeah, definitely [natural to see button and press it]."*

P10: *"In this case, I would again vote for VR, because of the realism and physicality. I enjoyed pushing the buttons and pulling the lever, because I found a lot of similarities on how you do it in this real life. So definitely, I, it was more enjoyable in VR than PC."*

Pattern 2: Feedback Gaps Identified (5/10 Participants)

Inconsistent feedback issues in the game were identified by five participants (P01, P03, P05, P09, P10). The most prominent one was with the sonar system, where both the active and inactive robots were indicated with the same red indicator, making their active state hard to understand. In addition to the sonar issue, P01 also mentioned that the elevator button lacked a green activation indicator, which all other buttons in the game had. According to Skarbez et al. (2017), both of these are examples of coherence failures, a phenomenon where the feedback from the game world doesn't match with the player's actions and could possibly destroy the player's belief in the Psi.

P01: *"I would love it to have the same effect for elevator because essentially it's the same button. I press it, it's green, I know it's activated. There was a sound that I registered, but at first I wasn't sure I pressed it. I'm like, 'Okay, is it working?' Oh, I hear the sound, it is*

working. Just a small thing—because everything else does have this green effect of activation."

P01: *"EMP was lacking some kind of visual effect because it was just the sound and I don't understand, 'Okay, what happened?' I didn't even get this EMP because I didn't read the description or something. There's some sound happening but no visuals. Like is it around me? Is it some wave? Is it only front? Is it all the sides? Maybe add some simple wave that I would also love to see where does it end."*

P03: *"Um, and what I wished was, um, that I get, for example, when I forgot, okay, this one robot there, did I already deactivate it or not? But when I pressed, uh, the button for this signal, it was still shown in red, like, all the others that might be already, um, still active... Um, so just an extra color indicator for this."*

P05: *"I do need some more feedback there. I do think that even like a slight vibration might help a little bit, but also kind of... I kind of want my hand to be stopped and I know that's not quite possible just now. But this kind of makes these interactions less satisfying that I would like them to be, and again, that's not something that I would fault you personally for because you can't change physics and stuff... It sounds weird but I think it's half the fun of actually hitting something, and again, I don't have a solution there. I'm just saying why it sometimes doesn't quite work for me and beyond."*

P09: *"Because the poles were gray and the rungs were yellow, but on the other cases, everything that's yellow is interactable, but on the ladder it's not... Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first."*

P10: *"One particular scenario that I remember was, when I was like disabling the robots they still showed red on my sonar scan, which confused me a bit. I would say a different color would be great to indicate the player, which robot is deactivated or which is not."*

Pattern 3: Color Affordance System: Strength and Contradiction (6/10)

Six participants (P01, P03, P05, P06, P09, P10) talked about the color-coded affordance system (yellow to indicate interactive objects, red to indicate enemies, and green to indicate objectives), which worked quite well as a whole except for the ladder and sonar functionality. Participants were taught to interact with anything that was yellow, and therefore, they naturally wanted to grab the yellow rung of the ladder instead of the intended poles on either side. P05 pointed out this exact conflict in their interview. The color coding system worked so well in

the end that it was able to teach participants a world rule, but then violated that same rule at the ladder.

P01: *"I think when something is up there and it's yellow and you just want to push it, this is just classic."*

P01: *"Because for example, I think that even when I scan—I use this scan and I see enemies—and even when I disable them and I scan, I still see them in the normal state, and I can't understand whether they're just standing or I deactivated them."*

P03: *"But when I pressed, uh, the button for this signal, it was still shown in red, like, all the others that might be already, um, still active."*

P05: *"I think it works, and probably the ladder tells you that it works too well. Or that you actually basically a little bit broke your own rule, and that it works so well that people started grabbing this ladder instinctively. But again, this is a pretty cool achievement already, I would say. Because I do think this is something we can absolutely learn from this."*

P06: *"It really felt like it made a difference. The instructions were really good and specific. They didn't vary over time and stayed constant. It actually felt like, as you described, when I see things I know exactly what to do. So the instructions were really good."*

P09: *"Because the poles were gray and the rungs were yellow, but on the other cases, everything that's yellow is interactable, but on the ladder it's not... Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first."*

P10: *"One particular scenario that I remember was, when I was like disabling the robots they still showed red on my sonar scan, which confused me a bit. I would say a different color would be great to indicate the player, which robot is deactivated or which is not."*

Theme 6: Experience Differentiation

Experience Differentiation is the final theme among the six primary themes constructed from the data. It mainly discusses how participants differentiated between VR and PC and expressed their preferences for one over the other by describing the characteristics that made them unique.

Pattern 1: VR Preference Near-Universal (9/10 Participants)

In the end, nine out of ten participants preferred VR. Four participants (P03, P06, P08, and P09) had an unconditional preference for VR, while five participants (P01, P02, P04, P05, and P10) had a conditional preference for VR based on improving aspects such as movement controls, session length, and comfort issues. P07 had a conditional preference for PC due to locomotion issues, but would prefer VR if locomotion controls were improved. None of the participants stated an unconditional preference for PC.

P01: *"I would rather play it in VR, even though I said that PC version was more overall kind of nice. I think I would prefer a bit edited and better version of VR. In this particular case I felt like it was more comfortable to play on PC, but I would love to play in VR because I feel like this interactivity is good for VR. These ladders and tapping and pushing buttons—it's all working well. You see your hands."*

P02: *"I mean, I guess VR, because it's more exciting than the PC one."*

P03: *"It's hard to tell. Mm-hmm. I guess, the VR version, just because, like, genre-wise, it's rather being sneaky, assassinating robots, and, that's why I want this mechanic of looking around corners, and, I can't do that in PC versions... For example, if it was a strategic game, then I wouldn't care about the VR version... Genre makes a lot of difference."*

P04: *"Well, I'm more curious to see how the VR version looks, okay? Well, I'm kind of, uh, I mean, I haven't much experience of VR, and I am also kind of curious to see how is this, how is this VR games?... So, if the convenience part and the comfort is same as the PC, then I will go with VR."*

P05: *"So for a demonstration of like 20 minutes I could choose either. I would probably choose VR for the novelty and for the slight edge on the immersion. If this was something like a 10 hour story game or something, I would probably at some point switch over to mouse and keyboard just because I can't play this for much longer without it being a problem for me."*

P06: *"I'll definitely go with the VR version... Because it is interactive. I felt like interacting with everything there is, and it felt fun. It felt interactive, and the last part with the bots, it felt really good and really challenging, and I didn't feel that in PC. So I'll definitely choose the VR."*

P08: *"Um, I think I would choose the VR version, because I had more fun playing it, and also the sense of immersion, I think works better with the VR version than the non-VR version."*

P09: *"The VR version... It's generally more enjoyable."*

P10: *"It's a complicated question. I would say VR, if there wasn't any comfort related issue while playing the game, because I enjoyed VR more. But if we are talking about playing longer sessions, I would go with PC version for the comfort."*

Pattern 2: Genre–Platform Match (5/10 Participants)

Five participants (P03, P07, P08, P09, P10) stated that a VR experience is also dependent upon the game genre; this finding resonates with Carroll et al.'s (2019) observation that game genre independently affected player experience ratings, with more interactive genres scoring higher. Although their study found no significant connection between platform and genre, they noted that comparisons across studies suggest VR's impact on presence may justify further investigation across different game genres.

P03: *"It's hard to tell. Mm-hmm. I guess, the VR version, just because, like, genre-wise, it's rather being sneaky, assassinating robots, and, that's why I want this mechanic of looking around corners, and, I can't do that in PC versions... For example, if it was a strategic game, then I wouldn't care about the VR version... Genre makes a lot of difference."*

P07: *"I have to say yes. Genre matters, I think. Because when I'm actually going to, going on, you know, the racing games or FPS shooting games or something like that, in that case, I think I would be really comfortable in Windows games than VR."*

P08: *"It depends I believe, it depends. Um, I think VR can definitely be immersive, but I don't think it can be immersive in every bit of genre, I believe. I think VR has sort of like a particular genre of video games that can feel very immersed with VR definitely. But there are also a lot of different type of video games or genres, which I believe a lot of players are, including me would prefer non-VR or just normal desktop version."*

P09: *"Because like, I haven't played any VR games in this genre and this felt like, really, really interesting compared to what I've played on PC so far for the same genre, and this gives you like, more, better feelings."*

P10: *"I think it depends on the genre of the game. If the game has a lot of physical reactions like this one, then I would sacrifice the comfort to enjoy VR's immersion."*

Pattern 3: PC Described as Competent but Forgettable (5/10 Participants)

There was an interesting pattern among five participants (P03, P05, P06, P07, P10) who experienced both versions of the game and found that they could not remember any particular memorable moment from the non-VR version. On the contrary, the most memorable moments in the VR version were often recalled vividly and spontaneously by the participants. This could be a potential novelty effect of VR, because every participant has probably played PC games like this before that incorporate all the mechanics that this game employed, and they felt routine for them.

P03: *"In the PC version? To be honest, in general, the PC version did not have that of a big impact on me, compared to the VR version. Most stuff I remember from the VR version because it was just more impressive, but the PC version, I guess... hard to tell, nothing specific, to be honest. Because all the interactions seem very familiar from other games I played."*

P05: *"In the PC version it didn't stand out all that much. So basically, you have had ladders in games since Duke Nukem 3D or you have had things like these lines that you slide over in like a Tomb Raider... there was nothing where I would say, oh, this was beyond what I would usually get from a game. But also, hey, it was already pretty, pretty amazing from what I would get for a student project where usually you don't get around to all these details."*

P06: *"What was the most memorable moment in the PC version?"... "Overall it was good, but nothing specific."*

P07: *"Uh, I think, there is no, you know, the PC version hadn't anything which is, you know, I remember properly, like, there was severe difference than the VR. However, the overall experience was really smooth."*

P10: *"I would say interactions. In the PC version, the interactions were something that I have done many, many times in other games, and it just didn't feel that different. The VR version, however, is another story. I loved on how physical and life-like the experience was. I honestly, like, enjoyed it more."*

Theme 7: Cross-Cutting Patterns

Several patterns were constructed from the data that span across multiple themes and carry important implications for VR game design.

Pattern 1: Individual Interaction Excellence Versus System Coherence (2/10 Participants)

Every single interaction with VR was rated as superior compared to its non-VR counterpart. Some participants had difficulty with the overall VR experience due to potential issues with locomotion and control systems. Therefore, while the discrete interactions were good, the movement mechanics in VR impacted the overall user experience. Thus, one of the most important lessons from this prototype is that it is possible for a user's experience of navigating through a virtual world to impact their perception of their entire experience, regardless of how well they interacted with the other components of the virtual world.

P01: "I would rather play it in VR, even though I said that PC version was more overall kind of nice. I think I would prefer a bit edited and better version of VR. In this particular case I felt like it was more comfortable to play on PC, but I would love to play in VR because I feel like this interactivity is good for VR. These ladders and tapping and pushing buttons—it's all working well. You see your hands."

P07: "If I'm thinking about any functionality, it could be, and every, if I talk about, you know, specific functionality, every functionality is better in VR, you know, the experience... But the overall experience is way much better in Windows, just because, you know, I think the design, game design... It's how I play the game in general, and the game design for VR wasn't really good."

Pattern 2: VR as Interest Activator (3/10 Participants)

The VR prototype successfully sparked interest among three participants (P03, P06, P08), who indicated an increased desire to play more VR games in the future. P03 inquired if there are more VR games of a similar genre. P06 explicitly mentioned they would play more VR games in the future with similar interactions, and P08 was able to discover for the first time how normal activities could be made interesting through enactment using VR.

P03: "Because I wonder why is there no VR Assassin's Creed? Actually, I think, isn't there VR?... There is, there is, okay. Because maybe I should try that now."

P06: *"After trying both versions, would you be interested in playing more VR games?"... "Yeah, I would be."... "Mostly for the interaction parts."*

P08: *"For me, it is the interesting part, like I said in the comparison earlier, like a very normal thing in a non-VR game can be a very interesting thing in a VR game, and that is the first time I'm experiencing this."*

Pattern 3: Game Knowledge Overriding Presence (2/10 Participants)

Participants with meta-awareness of the game world were capable of overriding presence effects by recognizing that the level of difficulty is very low or that there is no fall damage. This results in less emotional investment when they play the game, even though they experienced greater levels of perceptual presence.

P01: *"I didn't, even though I have the fear of heights, I didn't feel it in this game in particular. You saw me jumping down from there because there's no fall damage, and I cheated my way a little bit there."*

P05: *"I think VR is sabotaged a little bit because by the time I got to VR I already understood that these basically don't pose a threat to me. So I think the very low difficulty and the getting used to where they are and having been through the level already... the VR run wasn't like sneaky spy exciting in any way. Because I already knew what the robots were doing but they basically are too dumb to really hurt me in any way."*

3. Preference Robustness Across Methodological Variables

VR preference was constant for all methodological variables. The preference distribution was the same for both of the play-order groups, as shown in Table 3.1, which implies that preference is not an effect of novelty or recency.

Table 3.1: *Play Order Effects*

Play Order	Participants	Strong VR	Conditional VR	Conditional PC
PC→VR	P02, P03, P04, P05, P08	2	3	0
VR→PC	P01, P06, P07, P09, P10	2	2	1

Apart from that, VR preference was observed at all levels of experience. Experienced users (e.g., P09) demonstrated the strongest preference; however, there was also a significant number of novice users in both strong and conditional preference categories, as shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: *VR Experience Level Effects*

VR Experience	Participants	Preference Pattern
Experienced	P09	Strong VR
Moderate	P01, P03, P05, P07	1 Strong, 2 Conditional VR, 1 Conditional PC
Novice	P02, P04, P06, P08, P10	2 Strong, 3 Conditional VR

4. Design Recommendations

Recommendation 1: Clarify Ladder Grab Affordances (7/10)

P01: *"I thought I would climb ladder like this, and without your input I wouldn't have guessed it. I think I would just be stuck probably."*

P02: *"I think I understood that I have to pull from the sides and not the bars, but, like, if you didn't tell me, I could actually, like, okay, like, maybe it's the bars, I could feel like that."*

P05: *"My first try was kind of going on the rungs, on the step things. I think it's rungs, right? So I'm not sure if this is something worth adding, because you don't have to go either or. You could just offer both if you want. But I'm also not sure if I'm like the only person or if it's just something that's universal that people would try this."*

P06: *"The PC version was usual—as I am just interacting with it and going up, nothing fancy. But for the VR version, I was a bit confused why I am holding the side bars and going up instead of holding the steps and going up. So it was new to me, to be honest."*

P08: *"I believe there were no like text based or clear instructions when i was climbing the ladder, and as someone who haven't played many VR games for me that was new. So yeah it was a little confusing for me at the first, at the beginning."*

P09: *"Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first."*

P10: *"I got confused when where to hold on the ladder at the start of the game."*

Recommendation 2: Provide Locomotion Options Including Strafing (7/10)

P01: *"I immediately wanted to strafe left and right like I do here, but I couldn't for some reason on VR. I can only move front and back and that really disturbed me."*

P05: *"For the most part the Xbox controller also because of strafing because it's just a style that I play in. I'm basically never going in a straight line in a shooter type game. Also in a third person type game I'm probably also constantly doing the left and right thing around corners and stuff like that. So with that I was more used to it and it felt more like the default I'm used to."*

P06: *"In this case, it's of course PC because it was really easy for me to interact in PC. In some cases in VR, when I am interacting with the bots and we are face to face, I can't go*

behind it and disable him. So if he is facing me, it's certain that I am dying and re-spawning."

P07: *"I think if I had left and right movement, I would have chosen VR over Windows game for this project."*

P08: *"I think that would have been, um, much more easier to control I think. Because that's the control scheme that, uh, we usually use in non-VR games. So for me, I think, uh, I think that would have been a better experience for me personally."*

P09: *"I would say like not being able to move left to right on the VR version, that's the only thing."*

P10: *"I would say the controls were much easier to get a grasp on PC. It was not because the VR had bad controls, but rather because I'm more familiar with the layout on PC. I also love the head-based movement in VR, but I would have preferred if the rotation was smooth rather than snapping to certain degrees."*

Recommendation 3: Offer Rotation Style Options (6/10)

Preferred snap (1/10 — P09):

P09: *"Yeah, that helps with motion sickness for me... Yeah, I would not prefer that [smooth rotation]. I'm more inclined towards using snap and like, for smaller adjustment, I can just move myself."*

Preferred smooth (5/10 — P01, P02, P03, P08, P10):

P01: *"Also, with the right stick, the movement was choppy—you move and it's choppy. Whereas on PC it's smooth. I also would love maybe in VR game to be smoother motion of right stick."*

P02: *"Uh, I didn't like the moving in VR, which is always a tricky thing, because, like, whether it's teleportation or just, like, moving like that is just, like, um, annoying. Maybe if it was just, you can, um, the turning around was not, you know, like, snapping, but also smooth, maybe would feel a bit better, moving wise."*

P03: *"Um, yes, like, I think there are some people who don't like the smooth rotation or smooth movement in general... Yes, I don't have a problem with it, but, um, maybe a suggestion... maybe even if you only move your head for some centimeters, maybe in VR, you turn around for, for even more degrees."*

P08: *"Um, I think at first I need to experience that myself, because I don't know, if like, uh, people get dizzy or motion sickness in general, in that smooth camera movement. But I think I would have preferred the smooth camera movements. Definitely, yeah."*

P10: *"I would say the controls were much easier to get a grasp on PC. It was not because the VR had bad controls, but rather because I'm more familiar with the layout on PC. I also love the head-based movement in VR, but I would have preferred if the rotation was smooth rather than snapping to certain degrees."*

Recommendation 4: Theme 5, Pattern 1 — *Button and Lever Interactions Universally Successful (10/10 Participants).*

Recommendation 5: Theme 5, Pattern 2 — *Feedback Gaps Identified (5/10 Participants).*

5. Relationships Between Primary Themes

The six themes primarily constructed from the data are also interconnected. The following sections discuss how the themes can enhance, moderate, or contradict each other.

5.1 (Embodied Presence) and (Comfort Negotiation)

The strongest relational pattern among the themes is the relationship between Embodied Presence (Theme 1) and Comfort Negotiation (Theme 2). The two themes also had an inverse relationship. Because the same characteristics of VR that enable its distinct advantages (stereoscopic depth, head-tracked movement, physical enactment) are also the main reasons for comfort issues that PC gaming does not have.

All ten participants reported experiencing this trade-off, and a majority stated it was a negotiation rather than a simple preference. On the other hand, comfort levels were not predictive of participants' preferences, as all ten participants agreed that PC was more comfortable, yet nine still preferred VR. Therefore, it is possible that experiential value is weighed more heavily than physical discomfort for short- to medium-length periods when players are playing games such as those in this study.

P06: *"For the comfort one, I will say the PC. But for the interaction side, I will definitely say VR—it was really fun in VR interactions."*

P04: *"Well, for being more present and immersion, the VR one was better. I felt it much better, and maybe even it was a little bit too much sometimes. Because I'm not used to VR."*

P10: *"It's a complicated question. I would say VR, if there wasn't any comfort related issue while playing the game, because I enjoyed VR more. But if we are talking about playing longer sessions, I would go with PC version for the comfort."*

5.2 (Embodied Presence) and (Control and Agency)

The participant's perception of embodied presence was mainly influenced by the interaction with the specific action (e.g., push, climb, touch), while the control and agency experienced by the player are tied to navigation inside the virtual world. Many participants preferred the VR version based on the unique interactions it offered, but also criticized the platform for having bad navigation controls.

P07: *"If I'm thinking about any functionality, it could be, and every, if I talk about, you know, specific functionality, every functionality is better in VR, you know, the experience... But the overall experience is way much better in Windows, just because, you know, I think the design, game design... It's how I play the game in general, and the game design for VR wasn't really good."*

P03: *"Yeah, that's the only thing, the locomotion, otherwise, it was more satisfying in VR."*

5.3 (Control and Agency) and (Learning and Adaptation)

Frustration with locomotion in VR was increased by the gap between participants' familiarity with PC and VR interfaces. Participants evaluated VR's locomotion compared to years of developing muscle memory on a PC platform. They were vocal throughout the interview about important missing mechanics (e.g., strafing) in locomotion, which made the VR movement system inferior to PC.

P08: *"Definitely the non-VR version was easier. Because, um, once again I have, uh, familiarities with the controls with the gamepad or with the non-VR games. So like it was, um, sort of like a muscle memory to me... But in the VR version again I had to learn a lot of things. Um, there is nothing in my muscle memory."*

P01: *"I think these controllers are just like gamepads, they're really similar, they have the same buttons even. Just naturally I wanted to move, and on PC version I could do it but in VR I couldn't."*

5.4 (Learning and Adaptation) and (Interaction Design Quality)

Physical interactions that were legible (levers/buttons) had an almost universal success rate and did not require a learning curve. Mechanics like the ladder required participants to learn how it worked, which initially caused problems but was overcome as participants learned. The color-based interaction-guiding system had a high success rate across all interactions, except the ladder. The color yellow represented interactable objects in the world, but on the ladder, it was placed on the rungs rather than the poles on either side, which were the actual interaction points. This issue confused most participants.

P05: *"I think it works, and probably the ladder tells you that it works too well. Or that you actually basically a little bit broke your own rule, and that it works so well that people started grabbing this ladder instinctively."*

P09: *"Yeah, I think you're right. I usually reach for the yellow part of the ladder first."*

5.5 (Embodied Presence) and (Experience Differentiation)

Embodied Presence was the strongest predictor of platform preference. All eight participants for whom Embodied Presence was the dominant theme strongly preferred VR (four unconditionally and four conditionally). The two participants for whom Control/Agency was the primary theme (P01/P07) were the only participants whose preferences were weakened or inverted. None of the participants who experienced strong presence effects through VR preferred PC unconditionally.

P08: *"Um, I think I would choose the VR version, because I had more fun playing it, and also the sense of immersion, I think works better with the VR version than the non-VR version."*

P06: *"I'll definitely go with the VR version... Because it is interactive. I felt like interacting with everything there is, and it felt fun."*

5.6 (Embodied Presence) and (Learning and Adaptation)

Participants' physical effort in completing VR actions led to a sense of accomplishment, enhancing their overall immersion/embodiment. These findings supported SDT's (Ryan et al., 2006) emphasis on competence satisfaction and suggest that including learning friction in mechanics may be valuable, provided the difficulty curve leads to competence rather than continued frustration.

P08: *"I had to learn first, I was failing a lot, but when i finally did it that was a very good feeling of accomplishment, yeah."*

P10: *"Though I struggled a lot with the rope, I finally completed it after seven to eight tries and it was quite satisfying. It demanded a lot of physical effort, which was at times stressing, but really entertaining in the end."*

P09: *"It really generally takes more effort, that I can say... I think positive way that like gives lasting impression... Yeah, definitely [a sense of achievement]."*

6. Summary of Findings

These results clearly show that there is not only a difference in degree, but also a difference in type between VR and PC as gaming platforms. All participants indicated a higher level of presence within VR compared to PC. Additionally, nine of ten participants preferred the VR platform even though they acknowledged the discomfort and lack of control associated with it. The above indicates that gamers assess platforms using multiple, separate dimensions as opposed to a single dimension.

Concerning the level of sensory immersion experienced by participants during sessions (H1), the results indicated that the VR platform provided significantly higher levels of presence for all of the participants than the PC platform. Therefore, the results from the present study provided strong evidence supporting H1, and were consistent with both Slater's (2009) PI/Psi framework and Kiltani et al.'s (2012) embodiment model. However, the fact that presence did not result in emotional arousal among all participants complicated theoretical understanding.

Regarding the level of user control (H2), the PC platform was viewed as being easier for participants to control than the VR platform due to factors related to prior experience and familiarity, which provided explicit support for H2. However, the level of ease of control did not affect the preference of the participant. Participants occasionally indicated difficulty as part of the engagement, rather than a source of frustration, which complicates the assumption that ease of use is a factor in assessing quality.

Participants indicated that VR was significantly less comfortable, yet still preferred it. Although H3 was supported in that VR caused greater discomfort, it was not anticipated that this would negatively affect participants' preferences. The findings of this study expanded upon Weech et al.'s (2019) review by demonstrating how participants were consciously aware of navigating the trade-off between presence and cybersickness.

The transformation of routine activities into engaging experiences through physical enactment suggests that the primary value of VR does not lie in the intensity of its experiences, but rather in the qualitative change in how even simple interactions feel interesting in VR when done correctly.

In addition to the three hypothesis-based dimensions of this study, Learning and Adaptation provided more insight about the nature of VR experiences. Participants initially experienced difficulty with VR interactions, which later transformed into satisfaction as they adapted to it.

Interaction Design Quality distinguished between the quality of the implementation of a particular mechanic across platforms and generalizable differences between VR and PC experiences.

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